

ENHANCED ALGORITHM FOR ACCURATE IDENTIFICATION OF WATER BODIES IN SATELLITE IMAGERY

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Abstract: Satellite imagery is indispensable for environmental studies, particularly in water body identification. This paper introduces an enhanced algorithm that optimizes accuracy, image sharpness, and coverage through various combinations of spectral indices. The process involves acquiring Landsat images with 11 bands and integrating individual images with corresponding metafiles. Using QGIS software, all bands are merged to create a comprehensive dataset for analysis. The focus then shifts to developing and applying a novel spectral index, leveraging bands such as the Blue Band, Green Band, Near InfraRed (NIR) Band, and Short Wave Infrared 1 (SWIR1) Band. This proposed index demonstrates exceptional accuracy in identifying water bodies, achieving a mere 1.8% Total Error. The robustness of the results is validated against annotated ground truth associated with the satellite image. The study contributes to the field by presenting a systematic approach to satellite image processing, emphasizing the role of water-related spectral indices in enhancing accuracy. The meticulous integration of multi-band imagery and the application of advanced tools like QGIS underscore the practicality and reliability of the proposed methodology. The achieved precision, with a minimal Total Error rate, establishes the effectiveness of the spectral index in discerning water bodies, thereby advancing the capabilities of satellite-based environmental monitoring.

Keywords: Image Acquisition, QGIS (Quantum Geographic Information Systems), spectral indices, Multi-Band Imagery.

I. INTRODUCTION

Satellite imagery plays a crucial role in monitoring Earth resources, especially in identifying water bodies, which is essential for environmental studies, hydrological research, and disaster management. However, challenges arise due to the variability in water body characteristics, spectral signatures, and image resolution, hindering accurate identification. This paper presents an improved algorithm designed to overcome the limitations of traditional indices like NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index), which is known for its inconsistency across different landscapes. The algorithm involves a combination of multiple spectral indices, enhancing its adaptability to varying environments.

By integrating cutting-edge image processing techniques, the algorithm refines water body identification by considering both spatial and spectral information. It addresses challenges such as cloud cover, atmospheric conditions, and mixed pixels that can compromise accuracy in identification.

Temporal analysis accommodates seasonal variations, ensuring robust performance. The significance of the research lies in establishing a more reliable methodology for identifying water bodies, facilitating informed decision-making. This enhanced algorithm holds promise as a valuable tool for researchers, environmentalists, and policymakers, providing a comprehensive solution to challenges in accurately identifying and monitoring water bodies in satellite imagery. Comparative analyses are conducted to demonstrate the algorithm's superior performance and adaptability.

II. RELATED WORKS

Traditional remote sensing techniques, like single-band thresholding and two-band indices, often suffer from low accuracy, and determining an optimal threshold is challenging and time-consuming. AWEI can be employed to improve the precision of water extraction in the presence of environmental interference, ensuring a consistent threshold value. AWEI is specially crafted to enhance the accuracy of classification in regions with shadows and dark surfaces. It shows high efficiency, particularly in hilly terrains where pronounced shadows from the topology contribute significantly to classification errors [1].

Assessing the suitability of the Operational Land Imager (OLI) of Landsat-8's multispectral imagery for mapping land surface water (LSWM) using three Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) models, this study conducted evaluations within the Yangtze River Basin and the Huaihe River Basin located in China. The findings illustrate that all three models based on OLI NDWI demonstrate high accuracy, surpassing 95%, and robustness for LSWM. Specifically, the model based on NDWI model exhibited superior performance by combining the green band (Band 3) and the Shortwave Infrared 1 band (SWIR1, Band 6), referred to as NDWIO6,3, outperformed alternative models. The research concludes that Landsat-8 OLI images, particularly when utilizing the NDWIO6,3 model, can accurately and effectively map land surface water, providing valuable insights for water resource management [2].

Evaluation and comparison of various approaches for mapping open surface water bodies, utilizing six commonly used water indices and three different sensors (Landsat 7 ETM+, Landsat 8 OLI, and Sentinel-2 MSI). The research, conducted in the Poyang Lake Basin, China, assesses 27 combinations of algorithms and sensors, with NDWI-based algorithms showing slightly better performance. Landsat 8 and Sentinel-2 outperform Landsat 7 in overall accuracy, with NDWI and NDWI plus VI algorithms demonstrating the highest accuracy. The study provides valuable insights for selecting water indices and sensors for large-scale open surface water body mapping, offering implications for improved accuracy in such efforts [3].

Identification of open water bodies utilizing Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager imagery, specifically comparing spectral reflectance and digital number (DN) value images. The NDWI, obtained with reflectance (NDWI-Green/NIR), and outperformed other methods, capturing over 95% correct control points. The study recommends NDWI_35 with reflectance for water body categorization, highlighting its superiority when using the frequency histogram method. The results suggest that NDWI methods, particularly NDWI_35, are better suited for classification of water bodies compared to methods relying on a single band, emphasizing the importance of optimized thresholds for accurate results [4].

A study comparing various spectral indices, including Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI), Water Ratio Index (WRI), Normalized Difference Built-up

Index (NDFI), Enhanced Water Index (EWI), Weighted Normalized Difference Water Index (WNDWI), Automated Water Extraction Index (AWEI), Total Chlorophyll Wetness (TCW), Green Water Index (GWI), focuses on the identification of boundaries of surface water using Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) imagery emphasizes the effectiveness of simpler indices like GWI and Sum457 is highlighted, as they yield results similar to more intricate ratios such as EWI and WNDWI, potentially eliminating the need for a thresholding step in the process. Validation through visual inspection indicates the qualitative effectiveness of the selected indices [5].

Contrary to the usage of NIR Band in NDWI, MNDWI (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index) utilizes Mid-infrared bands like Landsat TM band 5. Implementing this modification proves effective in improving the visibility of open water features while efficiently suppressing noise from built-up land, vegetation, and soil. Unlike NDWI, MNDWI has the advantage of reducing and eliminating noise from built-up land, making it more suitable, especially in regions predominantly characterized by built-up land areas [6].

The introduction of a novel and robust Augmented Normalized Difference Water Index (ANDWI) is formulated to optimize the differentiation between pixels representing water and those representing non-water areas. ANDWI utilizes a broader range of spectral bands, including RGB, NIR, and SWIR1-2, to enhance water detection. A new method of thresholding dynamically using the Otsu algorithm is developed to optimize the effectiveness of ANDWI. The combined use of ANDWI and the cloud filtering algorithm contributes to more accurate and extensive satellite-based water body mapping [7].

Different spectral indices, including NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index), MNDWI (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index), NDMI (Normalized Difference Moisture Index), AWEI_{sh} (Automated Water Extraction Index - snow/ice), NWI (New Water Index), WRI (Water Ratio Index), and LBWEI (LST based Water Extraction Index), are employed for water body extraction. Results indicate that the LBWEI index exhibits higher accuracy, ranging from 93.66% to 97.63%, surpassing other techniques by 3% to 7%. The research emphasizes the effectiveness of the LBWEI technique in various contexts, including weather conditions, and recommends its use for rapid water body evaluation, providing crucial baseline information for algorithm development [8].

Challenges in mapping the distribution and dynamics of surface water are highlighted, emphasizing the limitations of Thresholding Single Water Index (TSWI) methods in selecting appropriate Water Indices and determining suitable thresholds. To overcome these issues, the study proposes a collaborative decision-making ensemble approach known as Collaborative Decision-making with Water Indices (CDWI). This method integrates four benchmark water indices, including NDWI, MNDWI, AWEI₀, and AWEI₁, demonstrating superior accuracy and robustness. CDWI proves less sensitive to threshold changes, enhancing its robustness and adaptability as a flexible method for mapping water. The framework of CDWI holds potential for broader applications with various satellite images, ensuring transferability and scalability [9].

This study utilizes Landsat 8 OLI images and spectral indices for demarcating land surface water in Zimbabwe, employing multiple algorithms. The LSWI plus VI model demonstrates superior performance, achieving an overall accuracy of 0.86, a kappa statistic of 0.70, and a reliability accuracy of 0.89. The study effectively generates a spatial distribution of land surface water across the entire country, emphasizing the applicability of OLI images for mapping at a national scale with acceptable accuracy. The research suggests further exploration into distinguishing water features based on alternative characteristics and datasets, emphasizing the potential implications for environmental policy and planning, particularly in identifying areas vulnerable to climate change effects and implementing mitigative measures [10].

The evaluation of the water status of ecosystems significantly relies on water-related spectral reflectance indices (WIs) developed based on characteristics in the spectra of water, soil, and vegetation. These indices find applications in agriculture and ecology. Several studies evaluate combining indices related to water and measures of greenness for the detection of water bodies [11].

A. Image Acquisition and Preprocessing

In the initial phase of the methodology, cloud-free Landsat 8 satellite images were acquired from the USGS Earth Explorer Website. A comprehensive dataset was assembled by obtaining 11 bands from the landscape, accompanied by their respective metafiles. To facilitate subsequent processing, these bands were integrated into a unified TIFF file using QGIS's merge function.

QGIS, an open-source Geographic Information System (GIS) software, serves as a versatile tool in satellite imagery processing. Its extensive capabilities, ranging from spatial analysis to map creation, make it an indispensable asset in handling and manipulating multi-band satellite data efficiently.

The significance of meticulous pre-processing cannot be overstated in ensuring the accuracy of subsequent analyses. Utilizing cloud-free imagery is crucial to prevent data contamination, while region-specific band data provides context and relevance to the study area. Advanced pre-processing techniques, such as band merging in QGIS, not only streamline data management but also contribute to the enhancement of subsequent analysis accuracy. Emphasizing a comprehensive approach, this highlights the need for a robust pre-processing framework, creating opportunities for more reliable and meaningful results in the field of satellite image processing.

Fig. 1 Workflow

B. Spectral Analysis for Enhanced Image Interpretation

$$((b2 - b6) / (b2 + b6)) - ((b3 - b5) / (b3 + b5)) + (b2 + (2.5) b3 - 1.5 (b5 + b6) - 0.25 * b7)$$

The above mathematical expression is a novel spectral index in this paper, meticulously formulated after extensive research on the reflective characteristics of specific spectral bands crucial for water body detection. The chosen bands - Blue (Band-2), Shortwave Infrared 1 (SWIR 1 or Band-6), Band-3 (Green), Band-5 (Near-Infrared or NIR), and Band-7 (Shortwave Infrared 2 or SWIR 2) - exhibit heightened reactivity to water features.

The careful selection of these bands stems from their unique spectral signatures, each contributing vital information for accurate water body identification. The Green band provides insights into vegetation dynamics related to water bodies, while Band-2 (Blue band) has sensitivity to shallow water. SWIR 1 (Band-6) and NIR (Band-5), with pronounced interactions with water content, along with SWIR 2's ability to capture nuanced details of water absorption, collectively enrich the spectral perspective.

This enhanced index formulation, refined through rigorous experimentation with diverse band combinations, represents a concerted effort to optimize accuracy in detecting water bodies across varied landscapes. The combination of these strategically chosen bands ensures a comprehensive spectral viewpoint, laying the foundation for advanced water body identification methodologies.

C. Processing Satellite Images Using Google Earth Engine (GEE)

In pursuit of developing an advanced spectral index for precise water body identification, a comprehensive approach involves rigorous testing of pre-processed satellite imagery. This assessment aims to determine the efficiency of the index in delineating water features.

Application of various spectral indices such as Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Automated Water Extraction Index (AWEI), Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI), as well as Adaptive Normalized Difference Water Index (ANDWI) are applied to the satellite imagery.

Fig. 2 NDWI

Fig. 3 ANDWI

Fig. 4 MNDWI

Fig. 5 AWEI

The images produced by each distinct spectral index play a pivotal role in extracting valuable information pertaining to water bodies. These outputs serve as crucial datasets for the comparison and evaluation of proposed algorithms. Analysing the strengths of the developed spectral index and its potential to surpass conventional methodologies in water body identification becomes possible through the examination of these resulting images. This process enhances our understanding of the algorithm's capabilities and highlights its effectiveness in advancing water body identification techniques.

D. Preparing Ground Truth Using Roboflow

Fig. 6 Ground Truth

Accurate measurement of performance metrics requires a comparison between algorithmic outputs and ground truth. In pursuit of this, a comprehensive ground truth is meticulously crafted through manual annotation using the open-source platform 'Roboflow'. This annotation process involves the delineation of distinct classes, namely the water class and the non-water class.

With precision in mind, water bodies are distinctly annotated with a subtle light greenish hue, ensuring clear differentiation from the background, which is uniformly marked in black. This rigorously curated ground truth dataset becomes an indispensable reference for evaluating and validating the algorithmic outputs, providing a robust basis for performance assessment and calibration.

IV. RESULTS

The suggested algorithm is utilized on satellite imagery to identify the existence of water bodies within the images. The obtained output is compared with the ground truth, which is the annotated satellite image, and performance metrics are determined to analyse accuracy. The output of the proposed algorithm is as follows.

Fig. 7 Proposed Algorithm

A. Performance Metrics

The performance metrics provide a robust framework for assessing the accuracy of the algorithm in comparison to the meticulously prepared ground truth data. Overall Accuracy (Po) offers a comprehensive view, ensuring a holistic evaluation of correct identifications. Recall (Sensitivity) emphasizes the algorithm's success in capturing actual water pixels, while Precision delves into the precision of water pixel identification. The F1 Score harmonizes Precision and Recall, presenting a balanced measure. Commission Error and Omission Error, for finding the False Positive Rate and False Negative Rate, pinpoint areas of misclassification, offering insights into false positives and negatives. The Total Error metric consolidates these aspects, providing a comprehensive gauge of the algorithm's accuracy against the ground truth, ensuring a thorough validation.

TABLE I

Performance Metrics	NDWI	ANDWI	MNDWI	AWEI	Modified Algorithm
Overall Accuracy	96.86%	97.97%	95.90%	91.40%	98.14%
Sensitivity	93.01%	97.51%	98.64%	80.27%	97.97%
Precision	99.49%	97.65%	92.16%	99.07%	97.62%
F1 Score	96.14%	97.58%	95.29%	88.68%	97.79%
Commission Error	0.34%	1.70%	6.08%	0.54%	1.73%
Omission Error	6.99%	2.49%	1.36%	19.73%	2.03%
Total Error	3.14%	2.03%	4.10%	8.60%	1.8%

Fig.8 Overall Accuracy

Fig.9 Total Error

Fig.10 Performance Metrics for Accuracy Analysis.

V. CONCLUSION

The results underscore the efficacy of the developed modified index, showcasing a noteworthy high overall accuracy and minimal total error. When applied to the Landsat image spanning the Chennai-Bay of Bengal region, the index distinctly delineates a substantial portion of water bodies across an extensive area. Its capability extends to capturing intricate details along the edges and in darker regions of water bodies. Consequently, the modified index stands as a foundational layer for the application of additional spectral indices like NDCI, CI, NDTI, etc. This strategic approach not only facilitates precise measurement of water quality parameters but also extends the accuracy to cover larger geographical extents.

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